

PAM 44.102 frag. 15 = Exodus 12:16-17: Another Cave 4 Exodus Manuscript?

Eibert Tigchelaar, KU Leuven

July 22, 2021

To the best of my knowledge, the Qumran Cave 4 fragment presently registered as PAM 44.102 frag. 15 and mounted on the IAA Plate 196, has remained unidentified from its excavation in Qumran Cave 4 (it first appears on the Excavation photograph PAM 40.978, then on PAM 41.502, but also on PAM 43.698) until the present day.

1 Textual Identification

Its text can with probability be related to the text of Exodus 12:16-17 even though few letters are complete. In line 2 יעשה is clear, and the traces of the following word seems to be the bottom parts of the letters לכם (including only the bottom tip of the hook of *lamed*). In line 3 באת is fairly certain. I propose to read the preceding letter not as *resh* or *taw*, but as *tsade*. Usually there would be more distance between the downstroke of *tsade* and the following letter, due to the base of *tsade*.

However, some scribes somewhat lengthen the downstroke of *tsade*, so that its base can reach under the next letter (this happens, for example, in 4Q184). If *tsade* is right, one may read associate the remains with Exod 12:16-17 and complete the lines with that text as follows:

[יאכל לכל נפש הוא לבדו] יעשה לְכֶם] ושמרתם את המצוה]	2
[כי בעצם היום הזה הוצאתי] אֶת צְבֹאתָ] יכם מארץ מצרים]	3

The Masoretic Text reads here **צבאותיכם**, but the Samaritan one reads **צבאתיכם** without *waw*, as in line 3.

The remains of line 1 are not decipherable with any certainty on the basis of the scant traces only. However, if one looks at the preceding text of Exodus 12:16, the traces would fit well with some letters of **כל מלאכה**: basestroke of the *kaph* of **כל**; basestroke and left top of the arm of *mem*; bottom tip of the hook of *lamed*, and perhaps the bottom top of the diagonal of *aleph*. If we identify the traces in that manner, then we may transcribe the entire fragment with reconstruction of the lines as follows:

[מקרא קדש יהיה לכם] כָּ] ל] מְלֹא] כה לא יעשה בהם אך אשר]	1
[יאכל לכל נפש הוא לבדו] יעשה לְכֶם] ושמרתם את המצוה]	2
[כי בעצם היום הזה הוצאתי] אֶת צְבֹאתָ] יכם מארץ מצרים]	3

2 Manuscript Identification

Identification of a fragment as belonging to a specific manuscript is based on a combination of textual content, material features, and script. On the basis of its content, one would want to assign the fragment to one of the Cave 4 identified (biblical) manuscripts with (parts of) Exodus, including the so-called Reworded Pentateuch manuscripts.

Few letter samples remain in the fragments, but none of the other manuscripts with part of Exodus has a corresponding set, so that it seems we cannot identify the fragment as belonging to one of the Exodus manuscripts. Of course, such a fragment, with biblical instructions regarding passover, might have fitted in a non-biblical text. We would then have to find a manuscript where the fragment first both textually, materially, and palaeographically. Alternatively, we may hypothesize that this is yet another Exodus manuscript (full or excerpted) of which only one fragment remains (see also 4Q15, 4Q16, 4Q18, 4Q19, and 4Q21).